

Studies in the Camphor Series. Part II. Synthesis of *iso*Nitrosothiocamphor and its Application as an Indicator in Acidimetry and Alkalimetry.

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According to the structure ascribed to thiocamphor in a recent communication by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 647), it was expected that the substance would yield an *isonitroso* derivative like camphor. The preparation of this compound has been possible by the interaction of *iso*amyl nitrite on thiocamphor in presence of sodamide. The corresponding camphor derivative has been prepared by a similar method using powdered sodium ethoxide in place of sodamide (Forster, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 232; Claisen and Manasse, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 530). The formation of *isonitroso* derivative can be represented by the following scheme :

The above synthesis leads to the constitution of *isonitrosothiocamphor* as described in Formula (III). The tautomeric change from (III) to (IV) is supported from its properties.

The substance forms a red sodium salt and is soluble in caustic alkalis forming a red solution which when acidified gives violet crystals. The alkaline solution when diluted changes from red to yellow. It is sparingly soluble in water and dilute mineral acids but soluble in common organic solvents like alcohol, ether, benzene, acetic acid etc. giving violet solutions. A very dilute solution in aqueous alkali practically seems to be colourless or very faintly coloured (violet). The colour change in acids and alkalis is very sensitive and it was, therefore, thought that the compound might be useful as an indicator.

Besides its capacity to form a sodium salt as described above, it also forms a benzoyl derivative and organic complexes with chlorides of cobalt, nickel, etc. with evolution of hydrochloric acid. The detailed description of these derivatives will be the subject of a future communication. All these reactions, however, show that the substance contains an easily replaceable hydrogen atom, for which it is slightly acidic in behaviour, and this hydrogen must be the one attached to the N·OH group. The substance should, therefore, be represented as in (IV). The formation of an isonitroso derivative is characteristic of substances containing $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-$ group. It is now found that this reaction is characteristic also of substances containing $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CS}-$ group, and that thiocarbonyl group imparts similar reactive nature to an adjacent methylene group. As previously described, a very dilute solution of the substance in acid solution is practically colourless and in alkaline solution it is yellow. Though the transformation of colour actually takes place from violet to yellow yet under the conditions of the experiment the substance may be considered as an unicoloured indicator. The transition range lies between p_{H} 8·6 and 9; p_{x} being 8·8. The above p_{H} values were obtained by adding equal amounts of the indicator of varying concentrations to equal volumes of Clark and Lub's standard buffer solutions. For example 0·5 c.c. of 0·04% solution in 60% alcohol, 1·2 c.c. of the same solution and 0·5 c.c. of 0·5% solution in 70% alcohol were added in each case to 10 c.c. of Clark and Lub's standard buffer solutions. Larger volumes of the indicator (0·5% solution) cannot be added, as the indicator itself is precipitated in that case. The same p_{H} range was obtained in each case.

From an observation of the range of transformation of some of the more useful indicators, such as methyl orange, methyl red, phenolphthalein, bromophenol blue, bromothymol blue, thymol blue, etc. it is interesting to note that the p_{H} ranges vary from 1·3 to 2·1, whereas in the case of isonitrosothiocamphor it is only 0·4. Special interest attaches to this indicator in view of its being (i) a thioketone, (ii) a nitroso derivative, none of which has previously responded to such colour changes and (iii) its availability for use for titration of weak organic acids. A phenolic acid (salicylic acid) has also given satisfactory results with sodium hydroxide and barium hydroxide solutions with this indicator. One of the defects of this indicator, however, is that it cannot be used in cold for the titration of sodium carbonate solutions. But if the solution to be titrated is boiled for 3-4 minutes

after adding nearly the required amount of carbonate to a known volume of acid, and the titration be completed by adding carbonate into the hot solution drop by drop, the sharp end-point is easily obtained. In this case large excess of dissolved carbon dioxide affects the reagent to a certain degree.

The colour change of the indicator may be attributed to a difference in ionisation of the reagent in the free state and of its sodium salt as shown below :

The stock solution to be used as the indicator consists of a 5% solution of *isonitrosothiocamphor* in a 70% solution of alcohol, one or two drops of which are necessary for each titration. With this indicator it has been possible to estimate the strength of alkalis like NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ solutions, strong acids like hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid, and weak organic acids like acetic, oxalic, succinic, and salicylic acids etc. The organic acids give the same result both in aqueous and alcoholic solutions. Though the results of titration are found to be identical in the case of both phenolphthalein and *isonitrosothiocamphor*, yet from the short *p_H* range of the latter, it is apparent that the results of titration with the new indicator should be much more accurate than those with phenolphthalein.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A solution of thiocamphor (17 g.) in ether (15 c.c.) was mixed with *isoamyl nitrite* (12 g.) and the solution was well cooled (0°) for half an hour. Sodamide (4 g.) suspended in sodium-dried ether (7 c.c.) was taken in a long necked flask (250 c.c.) fitted with a calcium chloride guard-tube and was similarly cooled to 0° for nearly 15 minutes. The solution of thiocamphor in *isoamyl nitrite* was slowly poured little by little over sodamide. The vigorous reaction was controlled by careful slow mixing of the materials and continued stirring. The red solution of thiocamphor slowly changed to dark red. The mixture was then kept at a very low temperature for another half hour, after which it was mixed with ice-cold water and shaken with ether to remove unchanged *isoamyl nitrite* and thiocamphor. The aqueous solution was then treated with dilute acetic acid

whereby violet crystals of isonitrosothiocamphor separated out. The crystals were separated by filtration, washed with water, and crystallised from alcohol or ether, m.p. 148°. The needle-shaped crystals when precipitated from alcoholic solution by means of water appear grey and when crystallised from hot concentrated solutions appear bluish violet. It is soluble in acetic acid (both strong or dilute) giving a violet solution and with aqueous alkalis it produces a red solution which changes to yellow on dilution. The substance, however, is practically insoluble in dilute mineral acids. The compound gives a red coloured precipitate with cobalt salts, a reaction which is very characteristic for the detection of cobalt. It is very sensitive and can detect cobalt up to an extent of 1 part of cobalt per 50,000 parts of water. With nickel salts it gives a greenish brown precipitate. The precipitate with cobalt is insoluble in water and dilute acetic acid, whereas that with nickel is soluble in dilute acetic acid. Experiments, now in progress, suggest that the substance is a suitable reagent for the quantitative estimation of cobalt. (Found: C, 60·62; H, 7·69; N, 7·08; S, 16·09. $C_{10}H_{15}ONS$ requires C, 60·91; H, 7·61; N, 7·11; S, 16·24 per cent).

The following data give an idea of the usefulness of the reagent as an indicator in acidimetry and alkalimetry.

TABLE I.

Strong acids.

Alkali required for 10 c.c. acid with

Reagents.	Conc.	Methyl orange.	Methyl red and methyl-ene blue (mixed indicator.)	Phenolphthalein.	isoNitrosothiocamphor.
H_2SO_4, Na_2CO_3	1N	10 c.c.	10 c.c.	...	9·95 c.c.
$H_2SO_4, NaOH$	0·1	10	10	10·05 c.c.	10·05
„ „	0·05	10	10	10·05	10·05
„ „	0·025	10	10	10·05	10·05
„ „	0·02	10·05	10·05	10·1	10·1
$HCl, Ba(OH)_2$	0·1	9·95	...	10	10
„ „	0·05	9·95	...	10	10

TABLE II.
Weak acids.

Reagents.	Conc.	Alkali required for 10 c.c. acid with Phenolphthalein.	<i>iso</i> Nitrosothiocamphor.
Oxalic acid, NaOH	0.1N	9.95 c.c.	9.95 c.c.
" "	0.05	9.95	9.95
" "	0.025	10	10
Succinic acid, NaOH	0.1	9.95	9.95
Succinic acid, Ba(OH) ₂	0.1	10	10
" "	0.05	10	10
Salicylic acid, NaOH	0.1	9.95	9.95
" "	0.05	9.95	9.95

The above results show that in the titration of a strong acid with a strong alkali the reagent is equally suitable like the more common indicators. At higher dilutions of the acids and alkalis the results are, as is to be expected, slightly affected, the order of deviations, nevertheless, being the same in the case of all the indicators. With weak acids (the standard solutions of which have been prepared by direct weighing), the reagent is quite as good an indicator as phenolphthalein, though owing to hydrolytic-effects the apparent neutralisation points correspond with a lower value of the alkali than in the case of the stronger acids.

SUMMARY.

1. *iso*Nitrosothiocamphor has been synthesised by the action of *iso*amyl nitrite on thiocamphor in presence of sodamide and its constitution has been established.

2. The usefulness of this substance as an indicator has been proved in the case of both strong and weak acids. The p_H range is rather narrow: p_H 8.6 to 9; $p_k = 8.8$.

3. The substance has also been used as a sensitive reagent for the detection of cobalt; sensitiveness being 1:50,000.

In conclusion, I desire to express my sincere thanks to Sir P. C. Rây to whom I am indebted for the research facilities in his laboratory. My thanks are also due to Mr. A. S. Bhattacharjee and Mr. R. Mitra of the Physical Chemistry laboratory for kindly helping me in taking a few observations in connection with the determination of sensitiveness of the reagent as an indicator.